

PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS AFFECTING PERSONAL DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: This article talks about the factors affecting the development of the person and healthy lifestyle. The culture of a healthy lifestyle, mental processes related to human health are discussed.

Key words: Health, healthy generation, development, psyche, mental development.

"It is known that our forefathers considered knowledge, education and training to be priceless wealth, as the most important condition and guarantee of human maturity and development of the nation. Of course, education is a product of consciousness, but at the same time, it also determines the level of consciousness and its development, that is, morality is the most important factor that shapes and enriches spirituality. Therefore, it is impossible to develop spirituality without changing the education system and consciousness based on this. Therefore, in this field, it is absolutely impossible to allow superficial official approaches to work that is not carefully thought out.

Creating a healthy generation is not only a task of raising it physically, mentally and spiritually healthy. Healthy people promote a healthy society.

Life activity related to human health is a unique living system, which includes various interrelated periods and stages during life. Among them, biological, psychological, social stage and system of factors have a special place.

When talking about the psychological factors of health, first of all, its characteristics in the form of a human personality and a whole unit are meant. Any achievements or solutions to problems that will be made in this place, first of all, will allow to find an answer to the question of what a "healthy person" is. The famous Russian psychiatrist S.S. As Korsakov wrote, the more all the properties and characteristics related to a healthy person are proportional to each other, interdependent, balanced and resistant to factors that threaten him from the external environment, the stronger and healthier he is. .

Adhering to a healthy lifestyle is actually a concept that requires psychological actions, skills and, if necessary, competence..

After all, health is such a state of a person's body and mind that he is not sick at the moment, and therefore he has the opportunity to fulfill many duties and tasks in life, and this state is a real opportunity to do good deeds.

At the same time, the state of neurosis, which can occur as a result of the negative effects of difficult situations and experiences on the psyche of the higher nervous system, is also a dangerous condition for a person's mental health..

The fact that a person is raised to be overly emotional from a young age and tends to stifle his character in situations where it is necessary to make a decision in conflicting complex situations opens the way to the origin of neurosis. The culture of a healthy lifestyle, first of all, comes from the way of thinking of a person, that is, it depends on thinking. When it comes to mental processes related to human health, the following are usually recognized: the correspondence of the subjective images seen and felt to the views of the objective world (the correctness and adequacy of the mental reflection); adequate self-perception; clear focus on subjects; good memory retention of information; the ability to logically process information; creativity (creativity, criticality of thinking, the ability to use the intellect productively and rationally); self-awareness; orderliness of mind (ability to control thoughts). Therefore, those who teach a child about the culture of a healthy lifestyle should first of all have certain qualifications themselves.

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